

Using NASA's TESS Mission to Characterize an Inflated Giant Planet

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Abstract

We report the discovery of TOI-640b from NASA’s Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS) mission, a hot Jupiter orbiting a newly evolved sub-giant star with a period of 5.0039 ± 0.0003 days. Using photometric data collected from TESS, we extracted the light curve to determine a ratio between the radius of the star and the radius of the planet. The stellar radius was determined using the TESS Input Catalog, which combines data from previous all-sky surveys (Stassun et al., 2019). CHIRON, a high-resolution spectrometer primarily used for radial velocity observations¹, was used to constrain the mass of the planet. We find that TOI-640 is a slightly evolved sub-giant star, with an effective temperature of 6440^{+140}_{-130} K, a stellar mass of $1.49^{+0.13}_{-0.11} M_{\odot}$, and radius of $2.24^{+0.36}_{-0.28} R_{\odot}$. The planetary companion, TOI-640b, is an inflated planet with a radius of $1.79^{+0.31}_{-0.25} R_J$, and a mass of $0.91^{+0.13}_{-0.12} M_J$. Some Jovian planets located in close-in, highly irradiated orbits are found to have inflated radii compared to predictions from theoretical models (Guillot & Showman, 2002; Fortney et al., 2007). TOI-640b is one of the most highly inflated giant planets detected thus far. The TOI-640 system is well-suited for further

¹<http://www.ctio.noao.edu/noao/node/847>

observation, due to the potential insight into inflation mechanisms that could result from the study of planets orbiting sub-giant stars, like TOI-640, as sub-giant stars experience an increase in luminosity which may play a role in planetary inflation.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Over the past few decades, the exoplanet field has expanded with the discovery of over 4000 exoplanets¹. Many of these discoveries are close-in Jovian-sized planets with periods less than 10 days, typically referred to as hot Jupiters. Interestingly, Jovian planets located in close-in, highly irradiated orbits are often found to have inflated radii. The mechanism behind this inflation mechanism is not well understood. However, Guillot & Showman (2002) predicts that the mechanism is likely due to the intense radiation received from the parent star. Inflated giant planets are defined as planets with radii larger than $\sim 1.4 R_J$. This $1.4 R_J$ cutoff is a result of current theoretical planetary formation models being unable to illustrate the driving mechanics that results in the formation of planets larger than this radii. While these current theoretical models are unable to recreate this inflation based on physical

¹NASA's Exoplanet Archive

parameters, there are currently ~ 125 confirmed inflated planets out of the 533 known giant planets as shown in Figure 1.1.²

A multitude of driving mechanisms behind the inflation of these giant planets have been proposed, based on trends that seem to, on average, result in planetary inflation. For example, many of these inflated planets tend to have an incident flux larger than $2 \times 10^5 \text{ W/m}^2$, and/or have an equilibrium temperature above 1000 K (Burrows et al., 1997; Bodenheimer et al., 2001; Guillot & Showman, 2002). However, there are also uninflated planets that receive significant stellar insolation (e.g. NGTS-8b and NGTS-9b) (Costes et al., 2019). Looking at Figure 1.1, we can see that there is not a clear and consistent correlation between inflation and flux received by the planet from its host star.

There are currently two main classes of driving mechanisms proposed for inflation. Class I is defined by theories that are based on stellar irradiation as the driver behind inflation, in which the added energy results in adiabatic heating, leading to planetary inflation (Bodenheimer et al., 2001; Batygin & Stevenson, 2010; Ginzburg & Sari, 2016). Class II is defined by theories that are not based on energy deposited by the host star, but rather claim inflation to be a preventative measure to counteract radiative cooling of the planet's atmosphere (Burrows et al., 2000; Chabrier & Baraffe, 2007; Wu & Lithwick, 2013).

²<https://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu>

Figure 1.1: The radii and periods for the known population of giant planets are plotted. Above the red line, at $1.4 R_J$, is the known population of inflated giant planets. This is where theoretical models require an additional, unknown source of energy to reproduce the inflated radii that are observed. This plot shows orbital period vs planetary radius, with colors scaled by the effective temperature of the host star. Here we see that on average, inflated planets tend to have shorter orbital periods. However, this could be a result of astronomers targeting hot Jupiters for observation due to observational restraints, such as poor weather or telescope time. Additionally, the colormap illustrates that these inflated planets also tend to be around hotter stars.

1.1 Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite

NASA's Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS) was launched on 18 April 2019 aboard a SpaceX Falcon 9 rocket. TESS is the first space-based, all-sky photometric survey designed to detect planetary transits. The mission plans to cover more than 85% of the sky in its initial two year mission, which is nearly 3/4 complete, and more than 94% in total after its extended mission. TESS has four cameras, each with a $24^\circ \times 24^\circ$ field of view. Each camera is made up of four Charge Coupled Devices (CCDs), which have a pixel scale of 21 arcseconds. During the two year primary mission of TESS, the space craft will observe 13 separate $24^\circ \times 96^\circ$ sectors in each hemisphere of the sky. Each sector will correspond to two separate orbits, with a total duration of ~ 27 days of observation of each sector. (Ricker et al., 2015)

To discover new planets around nearby bright stars – the primary goal of the TESS mission – TESS uses the transit technique. Specifically, as a planet passes in front of its host star (relative to our line of sight), it will cause a small periodic dimming of the total light. TESS observes in two modes, with two minute and thirty minute cadences. The two minute observations are a selection of 200,000 targets chosen prior to the launch of TESS. These pre-selected targets are nearby bright stars that would not only allow for transit detection of Earth-sized planets, but would be bright enough for detailed characterization of their atmospheres using current and future technologies. These observations are processed by the Science Processing Operations Center (SPOC) data pipeline developed at NASA Ames (?).

The resulting data from these observations are cleaned light curves with corrections applied to remove any known systematics, which can hinder any type of scientific analysis. The second data product is a full $24^\circ \times 96^\circ$ degree full frame image every 30 minutes. After the raw pixel files have been calibrated by SPOC, the light curves are then extracted and searched for planetary transits using the Quick-Look Pipeline (Huang et al. in prep).

Ground-based photometric observations have a lower signal to noise ratio due to the atmosphere turbulence causing distortions as a result of variable extinction in the Earth's atmosphere. TESS, being a space-based mission, does not have this resulting atmospheric distortion, allowing it to achieve a much higher photometric precision. TESS utilizes the transit method to detect transiting objects in the night sky. The information gained from observing these changes in received flux is the ratio of the radius of the eclipsing object to the target star. The transit method does not confirm the existence of a planet, but informs us whether it is consistent with a planetary sized object. Unfortunately, the changes in received flux can be a result of eclipsing binary stars, since a small star can be roughly the same size as a giant planet, allowing for the possibility of a false positive. However, the masses can vary by a factor of 100. Therefore the mass of the eclipsing object is required to confirm the nature of the object.

As mentioned above, follow up observations are required to confirm the type of bodies in the eclipsing system. Specifically these follow-up observations are required to further constrain the system's physical parameters such as the mass ratio

between the transiting object and the target star. Spectroscopic observations can be used to measure the radial velocity of the target star, providing an estimate of the transiting object’s mass, allowing us to determine whether or not the object’s mass is planetary. These follow-up, ground-based observations are a part the TESS Follow-Up Observing Program.

1.2 Transit Method

The transit observation method is defined by looking for periodic changes in received flux from the target object. When an object passes in front of a star within an observer’s line of sight, the transiting object blocks a fraction of the light received from the target object. This fraction is defined by the surface area of the transiting object divided by the surface area of the target star. Assuming spherical bodies, this reduces to the following equation:

$$Depth = \frac{R_t^2}{R_*^2}$$

Depth refers to difference between the light curve’s baseline received flux and the minimum point of the transit, R_t is the radius of the transiting object, and R_* is the radius of the star. Often, R_* is determined using observations from all-sky surveys like Gaia (Gaia Collaboration et al., 2016, 2018). This combination of data to constrain the stellar parameters, including Gaia, were done as a part of the TESS Input Catalog (TIC) version 8 (Stassun et al., 2019). While the transit gives the

radius ratio, R_P/R_* , the period, P , and the inclination, i , radial velocities give the minimum mass, $M_P \sin i$, and the mass ratio³, $\frac{M_P \sin i}{M_*}$.

1.3 Radial Velocities

The radial velocity method, also known as the Doppler method, is an observational technique to detect exoplanets. In a multi-body system, the orbiting bodies and the host star orbit a mutual center of mass. This center of mass is often inside the host star, or just outside its surface, when the orbiting companion is a planetary mass. As the host star orbits this center of mass, it appears to wobble from an observers point of view. The amount the host star wobble is dependent on the mass of its companion(s).

We observe the movement of host stars through redshifts and blueshifts in the spectral lines of the star. These allow us to then determine how fast the star is moving towards (blueshift) or away (redshift) from the observer. Ultimately, the radial velocity curve is extracted from the spectral shifts of the host star. Using the following equation, one is able to constrain the mass of the planetary companion.

$$K_* = 203.255(m/s)P^{-1/3}(M_P \sin i)M_*^{-2/3} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-e^2}}$$

³https://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu/docs/poet_calculations.html

Where K_* is the radial velocity amplitude, P is the period in days, M_P is the mass of the planet in Jupiter masses, M_* is the mass of the star in solar masses, i is the inclination of the system, and e is the eccentricity of the orbit⁴.

The earliest known exoplanets were detected using only the radial velocity method. However, it is extremely advantageous to try to detect exoplanets with both the radial velocity method and the transit method. If the planet transits, we are able to measure the orbital inclination, i , and this allows the actual mass of the planet to be measured, rather than just the minimum mass ($M \sin i$), from which the bulk density, and surface gravity can be measured. Additionally, transit observations can allow for more detailed characterization of the planets atmosphere.

1.4 CHIRON Spectrometer

This project used the CHIRON Spectrometer, which is a part of TFOP located on the 1.5m telescope at Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO) (Tokovinin et al., 2013). CHIRON is a high resolution, optical spectrometer, with a $R = 79,000$ spectral resolution. CHIRON is designed to monitor the radial velocities of bright stars, and has been used to detect low mass exoplanets. The spectral data from CHIRON is reduced using a modified version of the pipeline described in Tokovinin et al. (2013). The radial velocity data is then extracted from the reduced spectra data using a Least Squares Deconvolution analysis as explained in Zhou et al. (2016).

⁴Derived equation in Harvard undergraduate course, Astronomy 110: Exoplanets

Chapter 2

Methods

TIC147977348, dubbed TESS Object of Interest 640 (TOI-640), is a 10th magnitude star that was observed in sector 6 and 7 during the first year of the TESS primary mission. TOI-640 was observed through the 30 minute full frame cadence observations. Previous photometric observations of TOI-640, paired with Gaia parallax data, constrained the effective stellar temperature.

Knowledge of the stellar parameters, particularly the mass and radius, allows for constraints to be made on the planetary parameters due to the relation between the two bodies. As mentioned in Chapter 1.3, the depth of the observed transit is dependent on the ratio between the planetary and stellar radius. Knowledge of the stellar radius then allows us to estimate the planetary radius, rather than just having a ratio. Additionally, fitting spectroscopic data allows for the mass of the star to be determined. From the radial velocity data, we can get the mass ratio between the minimum planetary mass, $M_P \sin i$, and the mass of the star. The transit data

allowed us to measure the inclination, i , which then allows us to calculate the actual mass of the planet. Again, this shows that one can only know a planet as well as they know the host star, which has been made possible through previous space based, and ground based photometric surveys.

2.1 Extracting Light Curves from Raw Pixel Files

Since TOI-640 was not a preselected target for the TESS mission, the data from the TESS observation is released as a raw pixel file. Therefore, I made use of `LightKurve`, a Python package for Kepler and TESS data analysis (Barentsen et al., 2019). `LightKurve` allows the user to extract photometric data from the raw pixel files. This allows the user to create the light curve of the target star. Additionally, the `LightKurve` package allows for the user to create and manipulate photometric apertures and data to create a final transit light curve.

Using `LightKurve`'s function `lightkurve.search_tesscut()`, I was able to download the 10×10 raw pixel files from sector 6 and sector 7 observations centered around TOI-640 shown in Figure 2.1. These raw pixel files hold the photometric data pertaining to the amount of flux received by each pixel on TESS's CCDs. Figure 2.1 shows the raw pixel file of the 100^{th} cadence or image of observation from the 30 minute exposures in sector 6 and 7.

To best isolate the flux received by TESS from the target star, I constructed a photometric aperture. To determine the aperture of the target star, star mask, shown

in Figure 2.2, in both sectors, I defined a 6×6 box around the target in both sectors 6 and 7. To further isolate the target star, I then removed any pixels in the defined box that were not among the brightest 20 pixels out of the 100 pixel frame. This star mask (Figure 2.2) was then applied to every cadence in sector 6 and 7.

The star mask allowed me to isolate the pixels I would use to extract the light curve data that corresponds to the target star. In order to see changes in received flux, there needs to be something to compare to, a 'zero' point. To define this 'zero' point, I created an additional photometric aperture that corresponded to the "empty" space between TOI-640 and nearby contaminating objects. This mask will be my base zero. To define this aperture, the background mask shown in Figure 2.3, I selected all the pixels outside of my initial box of 6×6 pixels. I then removed any pixel that corresponded to the brightest 40 out of the 100 pixels in the entire frame. This allowed me to best isolate the pixels that did not contain any contaminating stars for the background mask. Figures 2.3 show the background mask for sector 6 and sector 7.

I converted the photometric data stored in the Raw Pixel File to a one dimensional array with the values corresponding to flux received by each TESS pixel using `LightCurve`'s function `.to_lightcurve()`.

To get a normalized flux for the target star, I subtracted the median value of the background mask from the flux of corresponding to each pixel of the star mask, and then divided by the median value of the flux of the entire star mask.

I used the data from the pixels corresponding to the star mask divided by the median value of the pixels corresponding to the selected background mask to get the normalized flux values, with a baseline at the flux value 1, as shown in Figures 2.7.

In Figure 2.4(a), at 1477 (BJD - 2457000), we see the falling edge of a spike that is a result of the data down link maneuver of TESS which occurs once every orbit (13.7 days). During the downlink, the spacecraft reorients itself to point the antenna towards Earth. This causes different parts of the spacecraft to be exposed to the Sun resulting in a change in the pattern of the temperature gradient on the space craft, this is then shown in the spike in sector 6's light curve (Figure 2.4(a)).

2.2 Correcting the Light Curves

Due to factors, such as stellar variability and spacecraft systematic errors, the light curves must first be corrected and flattened in order to be used to estimate the radius of the planetary companion. TESS has a pixel scale of 21 arc seconds. Due to the large area each pixel covers, the flux from nearby stars contaminates the light curve. To remove the flux due to the nearby objects, I used the known RA and Dec coordinates, as well as their known magnitudes and luminosities. To determine the amount from each nearby contaminant, I used the following equation to subtract the fraction of flux from each of the nearby contaminating stars compared to TOI-640.

I used the following magnitude to flux relation to isolate the fraction between the flux of a nearby contaminating star and TOI-640.

$$\frac{F_1}{F_2} = 10^{(m_2 - m_1)/2.5}$$

Then, using the RA and Dec coordinates of the nearby contaminating star to isolate the fraction of the flux from TOI-640.

$$Cont = F_{*,i} \exp - \frac{((RA_{TOI-640} - RA_{*,i}) \cos Dec_{*,i} \frac{\pi}{180})^2 + (Dec_{TOI-640} - Dec_{*,i})^2}{2\sigma^2}$$

$$\rightarrow \sigma = FWHM / 2.355$$

$$\rightarrow FWHM = \frac{1.5 \times 23}{60 \times 60}$$

In each sector, $\sim 17\%$ of the flux received is a result of the contamination from the 24 nearby stars. If the 17% of contaminating flux was not deblended from the light curve, this would have resulted in an approximate error greater than 9% when calculating the radius of the transiting object.

$$error \approx 1 / \sqrt{1 - 0.17}$$

Systematic errors in addition to stellar variability can impact the light curves as well. To get a flattened light curve, with a baseline at 1, I used a spline fit to remove the trends and variations in the light curve (Figure 2.6).

This then allows me to phase fold the light curve corresponding to the observed orbital period (Figure 2.7). Here we see a single transit comprised of all the transit data. I then merged the transit data from sector 6 and 7 using `numpy.vstack()` in order to fit a model to the data. In Figure 2.7 we can see there is a slight off-set in the depths of the transits in sector 6 compare to sector 7. This is an issue that we are working to resolve as we refit the system for further publication.

2.3 Estimation of TOI-640b's Radius

From our global analysis (see Chapter 2.4 for description of the global model), we know that TOI-640 has a stellar radius of $2.1 R_{\odot}$. From the depth of the transit, δ , we can estimate the radius of TOI-640's companion using the phase folded light curves shown in Figure 2.7.

Assuming the stellar disk of the star is uniformly emitting light and that the planet is not emitting any light from the side facing TESS (the 'night' side of the planet), we calculate the ratio of the radii by finding the depth of the transit curve. This is because the fraction of light that the planet blocks is proportional to the cross sectional area of the two bodies.

$$\delta = \frac{R_p^2}{R_*^2}$$

Using this equation, we found that the radius of the planet is estimated to be $1.65 R_J$. A planet of this size is considered to be an inflated giant planet.

2.4 Fitting Transit and Radial Velocity Models

To fit the transit and radial velocity observations of TOI-640b, we used the online version of EXOFAST (Eastman et al., 2019) made available by NASA’s Exoplanet Archive¹. EXOFAST is a publicly available exoplanet modeling code which utilizes the Markov Chain Monte Carlo method to jointly fit the transit light curve and the radial velocity curve (Eastman et al., 2019). Radial velocity observations for TOI-640 were obtained with the CHIRON spectrometer (See Chapter 1.5). Setting the priors as shown in Table 2.1, we used EXOFAST to constrain the physical parameters of the TOI-640 system by simultaneously fitting the model to the radial velocity data from CHIRON (Figure 2.11), and the transit data from TESS (Figure 2.12).

The priors used for the EXOFAST fit shown in Table 2.1 are T_{eff} and $[Fe/H]$. The temperature prior comes from the TESS Input Catalog, which combined data from different all-sky surveys (Stassun et al., 2019). The metallicity prior is a broad constraint assuming that TOI-640 is close to a solar metallicity. These are essential because they allow EXOFAST to constrain the mass and radius of the star, as there are direct relationships between the stellar temperature and metallicity and the stellar mass and radius. In the fit, we are using the Torres relation as explained

¹<https://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu/cgi-bin/ExoFast/nph-exofast>

in Torres et al. (2010). These relationships and constraints on the stellar parameters allow for the absolute planetary parameters to be calculated instead of just ratios such as the mass or radius ratio.

Priors	
Stellar Effective Temperature	6442 ± 136 K
Stellar Metallicity [Fe/H]	0.0 ± 0.25 dex

Table 2.1: The priors used for TOI-640 in the EXOFAST fit were calculated using the Torres relation between stellar metallicity and effective temperature, and stellar mass and radius (Torres et al., 2010)

Figures 2.8, and 2.9 show the resulting radial velocity and transit models, respectively, from the EXOFAST fit. In Figure 2.8, we see a radial velocity observation point at approximately $RV = -100m/s$. This point is shown to have large error bars, and lies off the model's fit. This is a result of poor weather conditions on the night of observation.

Target ID: TIC147977348, Cadence: 100

(a) TOI-640 Sector 6 Raw Pixel File

Target ID: TIC147977348, Cadence: 100

(b) TOI-640 Sector 7 Raw Pixel File

Figure 2.1: Sector 6 and sector 7 10×10 pixel cutout of the raw pixel files centered around TOI-640b extracted using the `LightKurve` Package. Both raw pixel files are the 100th observation. There are 987 total observations in sector 6 and 1086 observations in sector 7. Each of these cadences correspond to a single point of data in the extracted light curves shown in Figure 2.7

Target ID: TIC147977348, Cadence: 100

(a) TOI-640 Sector 6 Photometric Aperture

Target ID: TIC147977348, Cadence: 100

(b) TOI-640 Sector 7 Photometric Aperture

Figure 2.2: Pixels in red correspond to the star mask, as described in Chapter 2.1.

The mask here is shown on the 100th cadence of observation in both sector 6 and 7.

These pixels are what I am considering to contain the star TOI-640.

Target ID: TIC147977348, Cadence: 100

(a) TOI-640 Sector 6 Background Mask

Target ID: TIC147977348, Cadence: 100

(b) TOI-640 Sector 7 Background Mask

Figure 2.3: Pixels in red correspond to the pixels selected as the background mask using the method mentioned in Chapter 2.1. This mask is shown on cadence 100 in both sector 6 and 7. This background mask is used for each cadence of observation. These pixels are considered background flux baseline of the observation, they are treated as if there are no sources emitting light located within these pixels.

(a) TOI-640 Sector 6 Initial Light Curve

(b) TOI-640 Sector 7 Initial Light Curve

Figure 2.4: These are the initial, uncorrected light curves extracted from the raw pixel files from TESS using the python `LightKurve` package. Each point in the plot corresponds to the photometric data from a single cadence.

(a) TOI-640 Sector 6 Deblended Light Curve

(b) TOI-640 Sector 7 Deblended Light Curve

Figure 2.5: The blue points are the initial flux values from the raw pixel files. The red points is the deblended light curve. The deblended light curve is the isolated flux from TOI-640 without the contaminating flux from the 24 nearby contaminating objects.

(a) TOI-640 Sector 6 Spline Model Light Curve

(b) TOI-640 Sector 7 Spline Model Light Curve

Figure 2.6: This shows the initial light curve from sector 6 and sector 7 observations extracted from the raw pixel file using the `LightKurve` package compared to the light curve resulting from the spline model which was used to remove any trends from the light curve. Note, the transit occurring at 1505 BJD-2457000 was removed when calculating the depth. The shallower depth of this transit is a result of the downlink period of the TESS space craft causing a redistribution of the temperature gradient pattern on the spacecraft.

(a) TOI-640 Sector 6 Phase Folded Transit Light Curve

(b) TOI-640 Sector 7 Phase Folded Transit Light Curve

Figure 2.7: Phase folded light curve. Normalized flux plotted against time since center of transit in BJD. Using these plots, we are able to estimate the ratio of the stellar radius vs the planetary radius.

Figure 2.8: TOI-640 EXOFAST (online version via NASA's Exoplanet Archive)

Radial Velocity fit using CHIRON Radial Velocity observations.

Figure 2.9: TOI-640b EXOFAST (online version via exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu) Transit model fit using TESS photometry data.

Chapter 3

Results

From EXOFAST, we were able to constrain the physical parameters of the TOI-640 system (Table 3.1). We find that TOI-640 is newly evolved sub-giant star, $R_* = 2.24^{+0.36}_{-0.28} R_\odot$, $M_* = 1.49^{+0.13}_{-0.11} M_\odot$, $T_{eff} = 6440^{+140}_{-130} K$, with a planetary companion, TOI-640b. Using the transit observations of TOI-640b, we estimated the radius to be $1.65 R_J$, while the EXOFAST fit found TOI-640b to be a highly irradiated hot Jupiter, $R_P = 1.79^{+0.31}_{-0.25} R_J$, $M_P = 0.91^{+0.13}_{-0.12} M_J$, $\rho_P = 0.195^{+0.10}_{-0.069}$ (cgs), $T_{eq} = 1820^{+120}_{-110} K$, $\log(g_P) = 2.84 \pm 0.12$ (cgs), in a ~ 5 day orbit. The estimated radius we derived, $R_P = 1.65 R_J$, from the depth of the light curve for TOI-640 is consistent within 1σ of the EXOFAST determined radius.

3.1 Discussion

The TOI-640 system is very interesting due to the slightly evolved sub-giant nature of the host star, and the role stellar evolution may play in planetary inflation (Grunblatt et al., 2017). As we are examining the TOI-640 system, we are aiming to add another data point to the known population of inflated giant planets in order to aid in understanding the driving mechanisms behind this inflation. The evolved nature of the host star may be a contributing factor, since a stars flux output and size will change as it evolves off the main sequence. Further observations should better characterize the host star, leading to a greater understanding of its evolutionary state.

With a radius of $1.79 R_J$, TOI-640b is well above the $1.4 R_J$ cutoff which defines inflated giant planets. Being one of the most extreme cases of inflation, TOI-640b is well suited for characterization since it will have a large atmospheric scale height due to its low surface gravity. Compared to the known population, TOI-640b appears to be following a pattern in which closer-in planets to their host stars tend to be more inflated on average (Figure 3.1). However, it is important to note that prior to the launch of TESS and Kepler, surveys were predominantly discovering shorter period planets (<5 days) since they were unable to continuously monitor stars due to daytime and poor weather conditions. Therefore, the observed distribution may be biased since short period hot Jupiters are the easiest to observe,

especially from the ground, because the probability of transit is higher as¹:

$$p_{tr} = \frac{R_* + R_P}{a}$$

and the transit event occurs more frequently allowing for a greater number of observations, since one would only have to wait a few days to observe again.

Figure 3.1: The known population of giant planets is plotted as semi-major axis vs planetary radius and scaled using the color bar which shows stellar effective temperature. The horizontal red line denotes the 1.4 R_J cutoff defining inflated planets. As we can see however, there are ~ 125 confirmed planets with radii larger than this cutoff. TOI-640b is plotted as a star. There seems to be a trend where planetary radius increases with a decrease in orbital period. Additionally we see that these inflated planets tend to be located around hotter stars.

¹Derived equation in Harvard's undergraduate astronomy course, Astro 110: Exoplanets

By putting TOI-640b into context with the known population of inflated giant planets, I found that the inflation of TOI-640b was most affected by the equilibrium temperature, which is determined through the equation below, insolation flux, orbital period, stellar radius (for which $\log g$ is a metric), and stellar effective temperature. These all are factors in the resulting energy received by the planet from its host star, through relations such as the following equation.

$$T_{\text{eq}} = T_{\star} \sqrt{\frac{R_{\star}}{2a}} (1 - A_{\text{B}})^{1/4} \quad (3.1)$$

Where the T_{\star} is the effective temperature of the star, R_{\star} is the stellar radius, a is the semi-major axis of the planet's orbit, and A_{B} is the bond albedo of the planet.

Many theories for the driving mechanisms are based on added energy to the system, potentially due to the amount of energy the planet receives from its host star. Figure 3.2 illustrates the insolation flux of the planet (in terms of Earth's insolation flux) compared to the planetary radius. We see that there tends to be a clear pattern where planets smaller than $1.4 R_{\text{J}}$ tend to get larger with an increase in insolation flux. However, after the $1.4 R_{\text{J}}$ cutoff defining inflated giant planets, this trend seems to become less true. This could indicate that maybe insolation flux plays a smaller role in larger planets, however, there are still very few data points. The use of data from TESS will be able to discover more planets in this classification, uncovering the true population of inflated planets. As more and more data become available, planetary formation models will be able to use these data to constrain the mechanisms that produce planets larger $1.4 R_{\text{J}}$ using known parameters, rather than unknown energy sources. The TOI-640 system is one of these new data points

that will be used to aid new theoretical models in the goal to understand planetary evolution.

Figure 3.2: The known population of giant planets is plotted as Insolation Flux (S_{\oplus}) vs planetary radius (R_J) and scaled using the color bar which shows surface gravity ($\log g_p$), with TOI-640b plotted in a star shape. The horizontal red line denotes the $1.4 R_J$ cutoff, above which theoretical models struggle to recreate planets. Again, we can see there are ~ 125 inflated planets, however, there appears to be less of a correlation between insolation flux and planetary radius than between semi-major axis as shown in Figure 3.1.

Table 3.1: Median values and 68% confidence interval for global model of TOI-640

Parameter	Units	Values
Stellar Parameters:		
M_*	Mass (M_\odot)	$1.49^{+0.13}_{-0.11}$
R_*	Radius (R_\odot)	$2.24^{+0.36}_{-0.28}$
L_*	Luminosity (L_\odot)	$7.8^{+2.8}_{-2.0}$
ρ_*	Density (cgs)	$0.186^{+0.077}_{-0.058}$
$\log(g_*)$	Surface gravity (cgs)	$3.909^{+0.094}_{-0.10}$
T_{eff}	Effective temperature (K)	6440^{+140}_{-130}
[Fe/H]	Metallicity	0.00 ± 0.15
Planetary Parameters:		
e	Eccentricity	$0.116^{+0.090}_{-0.070}$
ω_*	Argument of periastron (degrees)	143^{+66}_{-38}
P	Period (days)	5.00399 ± 0.00030
a	Semi-major axis (AU)	$0.0654^{+0.0018}_{-0.0017}$
M_P	Mass (M_J)	$0.91^{+0.13}_{-0.12}$
R_P	Radius (R_J)	$1.79^{+0.31}_{-0.25}$
ρ_P	Density (cgs)	$0.195^{+0.10}_{-0.069}$
$\log(g_P)$	Surface gravity	2.84 ± 0.12
T_{eq}	Equilibrium Temperature (K)	1820^{+120}_{-110}
Θ	Safronov Number	$0.0442^{+0.0088}_{-0.0074}$
$\langle F \rangle$	Incident flux ($10^9 \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	$2.45^{+0.67}_{-0.54}$

Table 3.2: Median values and 68% confidence interval for global model of TOI-640

Parameter	Units	Values
RV Parameters:		
$e \cos \omega_*$		$-0.070^{+0.057}_{-0.061}$
$e \sin \omega_*$		$0.041^{+0.12}_{-0.074}$
T_P	Time of periastron (BJD _{TDB})	$2458470.32^{+0.92}_{-0.44}$
K	RV semi-amplitude (m/s)	$82.2^{+9.9}_{-9.5}$
$M_P \sin i$	Minimum mass (M_J)	$0.89^{+0.12}_{-0.11}$
M_P/M_*	Mass ratio	$0.000579^{+0.000070}_{-0.000068}$
γ	Systemic velocity (m/s)	39073.7 ± 6.9
Primary Transit Parameters:		
T_C	Time of transit (BJD _{TDB})	$2458469.7471^{+0.0018}_{-0.0019}$
R_P/R_*	Radius of planet in stellar radii	$0.0815^{+0.0025}_{-0.0024}$
a/R_*	Semi-major axis in stellar radii	$6.27^{+0.77}_{-0.74}$
u_1	linear limb-darkening coeff	$0.304^{+0.051}_{-0.052}$
u_2	quadratic limb-darkening coeff	$0.314^{+0.050}_{-0.049}$
i	Inclination (degrees)	$81.5^{+1.5}_{-2.6}$
b	Impact Parameter	$0.887^{+0.017}_{-0.023}$
δ	Transit depth	$0.00664^{+0.00042}_{-0.00038}$
T_{FWHM}	FWHM duration (days)	$0.1048^{+0.0052}_{-0.0076}$
τ	Ingress/egress duration (days)	$0.0466^{+0.011}_{-0.0092}$
T_{14}	Total duration (days)	$0.1514^{+0.0054}_{-0.0057}$
P_T	A priori non-grazing transit prob	$0.153^{+0.046}_{-0.025}$
$P_{T,G}$	A priori transit prob	$0.181^{+0.055}_{-0.029}$
F_0	Baseline flux	$1.000492^{+0.000097}_{-0.000095}$
Secondary Eclipse Parameters:		
T_S	Time of eclipse (BJD _{TDB})	$2458472.03^{+0.18}_{-0.19}$
b_S	Impact parameter	$0.96^{+0.27}_{-0.14}$
$T_{S,FWHM}$	FWHM duration (days)	$0.066^{+0.057}_{-0.066}$
τ_S	Ingress/egress duration (days)	$0.033^{+0.028}_{-0.033}$
$T_{S,14}$	Total duration (days)	$0.130^{+0.027}_{-0.13}$
P_S	A priori non-grazing eclipse prob	$0.1416^{+0.0093}_{-0.010}$
$P_{S,G}$	A priori eclipse prob	$0.167^{+0.012}_{-0.013}$

Chapter 4

Conclusions

In this paper, we presented the discovery of TOI-640b, a highly inflated Jovian planet orbiting around a sub-giant star. TOI-640b was discovered using NASA's TESS mission and the TESS Follow-Up Observing Program. The host star TOI-640, $M_* = 1.49^{+0.13}_{-0.11} M_\odot$, $R_* = 2.24^{+0.36}_{-0.28} R_\odot$, is a newly evolved sub-giant star with an effective temperature of $6440^{+140}_{-130} K$. The Jovian sized, planetary companion, TOI-640b, is an inflated planet of $1.79^{+0.31}_{-0.25} R_J$ with a mass of $0.91^{+0.13}_{-0.12} M_J$. TOI-640b is a close-in highly irradiated planet, with a semi-major axis of $0.0654^{+0.0018}_{-0.0017} AU$ and eccentricity of $0.116^{+0.090}_{-0.070}$. Further observations of the TOI-640 system would be beneficial due to the evolved nature of the star. Observations could lead to a better understanding of the inflation mechanics of Jovian planets, as well as planetary formation. Additionally further observations of TOI-640b could lead to a deeper understanding of its atmospheric composition, and its role in the planet's inflation.

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